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Improving Learner Science Achievement through e-Learning Platforms

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Abstract

The study evaluated the effectiveness of e-learning platforms in improving Science achievement among Grade VI pupils at Southville Elementary School. A total of 54 pupils were divided equally into traditional instruction and e-learning groups. The research used matched pairing and statistical methods, including mean, standard deviation, paired t-tests, and Cohen's d. Initial findings revealed that both groups had the same mean pre-test score of 7.52 (SD = 1.87), indicating a satisfactory performance. During the formative tests, the e-learning group outperformed the Traditional Instruction Group, with mean scores of 50.41 (SD = 3.92) and 46.70 (SD = 4.42), respectively. In the post-test, the e-learning group again showed superior performance, with a mean score of 15.44 (SD = 1.72) compared to the traditional instruction group's 14.15 (SD = 2.05), both of which were at a very satisfactory level. Statistical analysis confirmed a significant difference between the groups in both formative tests [(t(52) = 3.26; p<0.01], with a moderate effect size (d = 0.88), and post-tests [(t(52) = 2.52; p<0.05], with a moderate effect size (d = 0.68). Furthermore, the within-group analysis revealed significant differences between pre- and post-test scores. For the traditional instruction group, the post-test scores were significantly higher than the pre-test scores [(t(26) = 12.17; p<0.01], with a large effect size (d = 4.41). Similarly, the e-learning group showed significant improvement [(t(26) = 15.66; p<0.01], with a large effect size (d = 3.38). It is concluded that e-learning platforms significantly enhance pupil performance in Science. Also, both null hypotheses in the study were rejected.

Keywords: *e-Learning, traditional instruction, achievement, effectiveness, assessment*

Introduction

Education is crucial in society and vital for individual development and a better future. Improving students' knowledge, skills, and competency is a primary concern for educational institutions. Teaching 21st-century students poses a unique challenge for educators, who must adapt their strategies to meet the needs of modern learners. Many students struggle with teachers' traditional methods, which fail to engage them effectively. Schools, therefore, must leverage new technologies and innovations, such as blogs, wikis, social networking sites, and virtual learning environments (VLEs), to create more dynamic and effective educational experiences. These "first-order" innovations, as described by Selwyn (2010), are critical in transforming the academic climate, aligning with the global shift toward more interactive and technology-rich learning environments.

To meet global and local competitiveness goals, as outlined in the K-12 Law, integrating Information and Communication Technology (ICT) into the education system is essential. Teachers play a crucial role in motivating learners and ensuring the quality of education meets international standards. Research emphasizes that student motivation and engagement in lessons should be a priority for both institutions and educators (Hsu, 1999). In response, the Department of Education (DepEd) in the Philippines issued orders such as DepEd Order No. 78 (2010) and DepEd Order No. 42 (2016) to promote the use of multimedia and technology in classrooms, thereby shifting from instructor-focused to learner-centered methods. These orders highlight the importance of multimedia in enhancing the teaching-learning process, making complex concepts more accessible through interactive and integrated instructional materials (Crosby & Stelovsky, 2014).

As technology increasingly influences education, e-learning strategies have become more prominent, providing new methods for effective knowledge dissemination and learning. The rise of e-learning is seen as a critical component in the evolution of educational practices, enabling quicker and more effective learning (Smith et al., 2015). However, unmotivated students, extracurricular activities, government holidays, and natural disasters like typhoons can disrupt the learning flow, as Molintapang (2013) noted. To address these challenges, the study proposes an interactive social media platform (offline website) to assist teachers in engaging students in a more enjoyable and motivating learning process. This approach aims to overcome the barriers to learning and enhance the overall educational experience in a manner that aligns with the needs of 21st-century learners.

The OECD (2014) has embarked on an initiative to measure innovation in education, aiming to identify which new teaching methods and school organizations truly enhance educational performance. However, distinguishing genuine innovations from changes that may negatively impact student achievement remains challenging. To address this, there is a need for evidence-based knowledge to define true innovations, leveraging randomized or quasi-randomized experiments to a greater extent. e-Learning, as an educational innovation, utilizes information and communication technology (ICT) to support learning, ranging from simple online course materials to fully online programs. This approach is designed to increase accessibility, reduce costs, and improve academic performance, making education more inclusive and efficient.

Research indicates that e-learning significantly enhances students' academic outcomes compared to traditional face-to-face instruction. Studies by Holley (2012) and OECD (2010) demonstrate that students engaged in e-learning achieve better grades, highlighting the

effectiveness of this technology-enabled instructional method. Moreover, greater engagement in e-learning correlates with improved academic performance, as shown in a longitudinal study by Isola (2010). The growing popularity of e-learning, driven by its positive impact on student performance and higher educational institutions' increasing adoption of virtual learning systems, underscores its role as a transformative innovation in education. In the Philippines, the rise of multimedia technology further supports this trend, as it has become an integral tool for providing computer-based instruction, contributing to the overall improvement in the quality of education.

Research Questions

The study's main objective is to determine the effectiveness of e-learning platforms in improving the achievement in Science of Grade VI pupils in Southville Elementary School. Specifically, it sought answers to the following:

1. What are the pre-test mean scores of the traditional instruction and e-learning groups?
2. What are the mean scores of the traditional instruction and e-learning groups on the formative test?
3. What are the post-test mean scores of traditional instruction and e-learning groups?
4. Is there a significant difference between the mean scores of the traditional instruction group and the e-learning group on the pre-test, post-test, and formative tests?
5. Is there a significant difference between the mean scores on the pre-test and post-test of the traditional instruction group and the e-learning group?

Literature Review

Teachers' Roles in Educational Innovation

Teachers are the key movers in instilling curriculum content in students. They use innovative materials beyond traditional methods and/or blend them together to match the needs of both the students and the curriculum.

According to Falch and Constantin (2015), teachers drive educational innovation within the classroom. They argue that while various factors influence student skill development, teacher behavior is particularly responsive to policy interventions and can impact learning outcomes. Effective innovation requires teachers who are willing to experiment and adapt their methods, though measuring these innovative skills is challenging. High-quality teachers who consistently enhance student achievement are typically better equipped to implement and assess innovative practices that can be online and offline with varied features (Francia, 2022). However, the reliance on other teachers' successful experiments indicates that traditional measures of teacher quality may not fully capture the ability to innovate.

Goatley and Johnson (2013) stress that innovation is essential to effective teaching in a rapidly changing society. They highlight examples of successful innovations, often initiated through collaboration that evolve into broader applications. Innovation in education requires educators to challenge existing methods, explore new possibilities, and engage in collective experimentation. This process is supported by professional environments that encourage diverse ideas and data-driven assessments of outcomes. The authors argue that building capacity for innovation involves creating open platforms for sharing imaginative solutions and continuously assessing the impact of these innovations on teaching and learning. Also, Lim (2016) examines the potential of adopting online blended learning, a common practice in advanced educational environments in Asia and America, and finds that while online synchronous learning is favored for its potential to enhance governance and collaboration, DLSU's academic culture leans towards asynchronous learning environments. Despite the general acceptance of e-learning among students and faculty, effective content management and training are critical to successfully implementing these innovations. It found the need to tailor technological advancements to local contexts and emphasize the importance of training and content delivery to meet specific educational needs.

De Luna (2015) argues that continuous innovation is essential for keeping educational practices relevant to evolving social, cultural, and economic realities. Technological innovations, such as e-books, have impacted educational management systems, necessitating shifts in pedagogical approaches. These changes are both technical and paradigmatic, altering how we perceive and engage with the learning process. The study points out that these innovations, while beneficial, are culturally specific and relative, suggesting that their success depends on how well they are integrated into the existing educational and social fabric. The study also emphasizes the transformative potential of technology in education but also highlights the challenges of adapting these tools to different contexts and populations.

Abulon (2014) focuses on the role of effective teaching in curriculum planning and pre-service teacher education. The study identifies key benchmarks for teacher competency, including content mastery, pedagogical knowledge, and the use of innovative teaching methods like interactive teaching styles and ICT. It argues that these elements should be central to pre-service training programs to prepare future teachers for the demands of modern classrooms. The study also suggests that in-service teachers should engage in continuous professional development to maintain their effectiveness, advocating for practices like volunteering and community engagement as part of a comprehensive approach to teaching.

E-Learning in Education

The discussion of e-learning and instructional materials further underscores the importance of innovation in education. Fairlie and

Robinson (2013) and Abimbade (2012) discuss the transformative potential of e-learning, which enhances accessibility and efficiency in education. However, the effectiveness of these technologies depends on their thoughtful integration into the curriculum. Valdez (2011) and DfES (2013) emphasized that instructional materials make learning more engaging and interactive. When used effectively, these tools can improve student performance by catering to diverse learning needs and promoting active participation in the learning process.

Falck et al. (2014) provide a clear view of the impact of e-learning on student achievement. Their analysis of data from the Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) reveals that the effectiveness of e-learning varies depending on its application. Using classroom computers for research positively impacts student achievement, while using them for practicing skills can have negative effects. This suggests that e-learning is most beneficial for tasks lacking effective traditional alternatives. The mixed results highlight the need for careful consideration of how technology is integrated into the classroom, as its success depends largely on the specific educational context and the nature of its use.

Finally, the studies reviewed by Bulman and Fairlie (2014) confirm the mixed effects of computer use on educational outcomes. They distinguish between the effects of home versus school use of computers, noting that while technology can enhance learning, it can also be a distraction if not properly managed. The review highlights the importance of context in determining the effectiveness of educational technologies, with successful implementation requiring a balance between innovation and traditional teaching methods. The findings from studies in the Philippines and other countries emphasize that while ICT has the potential to transform education, its success depends on thoughtful integration into existing educational practices and a clear understanding of its limitations and benefits.

Methodology

This study utilized a quasi-experimental design to evaluate the effectiveness of an e-learning platform in improving Science performance among Grade VI students at Southville Elementary School. The research compared two groups: one taught using traditional instructional (K6) materials and the other using e-learning materials. Participants were selected from a pool of 90 students through match pairing based on pre-test scores, resulting in 68 participants. The research instruments included pre-test and post-test assessments, supported by summative and formative evaluations adapted from Department of Education tools. Experts validated the e-learning platform before implementation, known as “Science Offline Application (SOlapp),” an electronic type of book that is easily accessible via electronic gadgets and composed of discussions and illustrations following the standard Science Contents.

The experiment ran for the entire third grading period following the curricular contents and competencies, with formative tests administered weekly. Statistical analysis included mean percentage scores, standard deviation, paired t-tests to assess significant differences between groups, and Cohen’s *d* to measure effect size. The results aimed to determine the impact of e-learning on student performance compared to traditional instructional methods. The participants’ information was highly treated with confidentiality. There was informed consent and the students and parents were informed of the study objectives, giving them the freedom to participate or withdraw. All processes and permits were secured following the research ethics committee and school protocols.

Results and Discussion

This section provides a comprehensive presentation of the results, analysis, and interpretation of data obtained from the respondents during the implementation of this quasi-experiment study on the effectiveness of e-learning in science for Grade VI students at Southville Elementary School.

Table 1. *Pre-Test Mean Scores of the Traditional Instruction Group and E-Learning Group*

<i>Group</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Skewness</i>	<i>Description</i>
Traditional Instruction	7.52	1.87	-0.60	Satisfactory
E-Learning	7.52	1.87	-0.60	Satisfactory

Legend: 0.00-2.50 Poor; 2.51-7.50 Fairly Satisfactory; 7.51-12.50 Satisfactory; 12.51-17.50 Very Satisfactory; 17.51-20.00 Excellent

The study compared the performance of Grade VI students in a Traditional Instruction Group and an e-learning group, with both groups initially showing similar performance in the pre-test, achieving a mean score of 7.52 (SD = 1.87), indicating a satisfactory level of competency in Science. The skewness value of -0.60 suggested that most students scored between 8 and 12 points, aligning with the satisfactory performance level. The implementation of the e-learning platform aimed to explore its effectiveness in delivering instructional outcomes comparable to or better than traditional methods. Despite the potential advantages of e-learning, the study acknowledges that various factors, some unrelated to ICT, can negatively influence student performance.

In the formative test, the e-learning group outperformed the Traditional Instruction Group, with mean scores of 50.41 (SD = 3.92) and 46.70 (SD = 4.42), respectively, both indicating a very satisfactory level of performance. The Traditional Instruction Group's skewness of 0.02 indicated that many students scored slightly below their mean. In contrast, the e-learning group's skewness of -0.91 showed that more students achieved scores above the mean, reflecting very satisfactory to excellent performance. These results suggest that the e-learning platform may offer advantages over traditional methods, as it contributed to higher achievement levels among students in the e-learning group.

Table 2. *Formative Test Mean Scores of the Traditional Instruction Group and e-Learning Group*

Competency Areas	Group	Mean	SD	Skewness	Description
Force*	traditional instruction	3.30	0.91	-0.32	Satisfactory
	e-learning	3.59	0.89	0.23	Very Satisfactory
Kind of Forces*	traditional instruction	3.00	0.68	0.00	Satisfactory
	e-learning	3.48	0.94	0.36	Satisfactory
Friction**	traditional instruction	6.63	1.15	-0.01	Very Satisfactory
	e-learning	6.96	1.02	0.08	Very Satisfactory
Factors affecting Friction*	traditional instruction	3.41	0.84	0.31	Satisfactory
	e-learning	3.81	0.88	0.35	Very Satisfactory
Newton's Law of Motion**	traditional instruction	6.81	1.57	-0.44	Very Satisfactory
	e-learning	7.48	1.12	0.67	Very Satisfactory
Potential and Kinetic Energy*	traditional instruction	3.33	0.88	-0.00	Satisfactory
	e-learning	3.56	0.75	0.97	Very Satisfactory
Forms of Energy*	traditional instruction	3.48	1.05	-0.05	Very Satisfactory
	e-learning	3.78	0.70	0.33	Very Satisfactory
Materials that produce Energy**	traditional instruction	6.85	1.03	-0.37	Very Satisfactory
	e-learning	7.04	1.02	0.16	Very Satisfactory
Producing Electricity*	traditional instruction	3.19	0.88	0.35	Satisfactory
	e-learning	3.41	0.80	0.57	Satisfactory
Simple Machine**	traditional instruction	6.70	1.03	-0.03	Very Satisfactory
	e-learning	7.30	0.82	0.27	Very Satisfactory
Overall***	traditional instruction	46.70	4.42	0.02	Very Satisfactory
	e-learning	50.41	3.92	-0.91	Very Satisfactory

The table reveals that the e-learning group consistently outperformed the Traditional Instruction Group across various competency areas in Science. Specifically, the e-learning group achieved satisfactory levels in "Kind of Forces" ($\bar{x} = 3.48$; $SD = 0.94$) and "Producing Electricity" ($\bar{x} = 3.41$; $SD = 0.80$) and performed at satisfactory to excellent levels in areas such as Force ($\bar{x} = 3.59$; $SD = 0.89$), Friction ($\bar{x} = 6.96$; $SD = 1.02$), Newton's Law of Motion ($\bar{x} = 7.48$; $SD = 1.12$), and Simple Machines ($\bar{x} = 7.30$; $SD = 0.82$). Positive skewness across these areas indicates that most students scored below the mean yet still maintained satisfactory performance. Notably, the e-learning group's mean scores in all areas surpassed those of the Traditional Instruction Group. The findings suggest that the Traditional Instruction Group maintained a very satisfactory level of competency, while the e-learning group achieved excellent performance. The distribution of student performance indicates that the Traditional Instruction Group's scores were scattered between satisfactory and very satisfactory levels. In contrast, the e-learning group showed a concentration of scores in the very satisfactory and excellent range. This higher performance level in the e-learning group can be attributed to the platform's ability to foster greater student engagement and participation.

Table 3. *Post-test Mean Scores of the Traditional Instruction Group and E-Learning Group*

Group	Mean	SD	Skewness	Description
Traditional Instruction	14.15	2.05	-0.39	Very Satisfactory
E-Learning	15.44	1.72	-0.32	Very Satisfactory

Legend: 0.00-2.50 Poor; 2.51-7.50 Fairly Satisfactory; 7.51-12.50 Satisfactory; 12.51-17.50 Very Satisfactory; 17.51-20.00 Excellent

Table 3 indicates that the traditional instruction and e-learning groups performed very satisfactorily in the post-test, with mean scores of 14.15 ($SD = 2.05$) and 15.44 ($SD = 1.72$), respectively. The Traditional Instruction Group showed a skewness of -0.39, with most students scoring between 15 and 17 points. At the same time, the e-learning group had a skewness of -0.32, with many students scoring between 16 and 18 points, reflecting a mix of very satisfactory and excellent performance. These results suggest that both instructional methods effectively enhanced learning competencies in Science, with the e-learning group showing a slightly higher performance, including some students reaching an excellent level. This aligns with findings by Novo-Corti, Varela-Candamio, and Ramil-Diaz (2013), who noted improved student performance with a mix of e-learning and face-to-face instruction.

Table 4. *Results of the Test of Significant Difference Between the Mean Performance of the Two Groups*

Test	Group	Mean Difference	Df	Computed t-value	Effect Size	Description
Formative test	Traditional Instruction	3.704	52	3.26**	0.88	Moderate
	e-Learning					
Post-test	Traditional Instruction	1.296	52	2.52*	0.68	Moderate
	e-Learning					

** $p < .01$; * $p < .05$

The findings in Table 4 demonstrate a significant difference between the mean scores of the traditional and e-learning groups in both formative tests and post-tests, with the e-learning group consistently outperforming the Traditional Instruction Group. The t-test results

for the formative tests [(t(52) = 3.26; $p < 0.01$], with a mean difference of 3.704 and an effect size ($d = 0.88$), indicate that the e-learning platform had a moderate impact on student performance. Similarly, the post-test analysis revealed a significant difference [(t(52) = 2.52; $p < 0.05$], with a mean difference of 1.296 and an effect size ($d = 0.68$), showing that the e-Learning platform also moderately improved exit performance. These results imply that students in the e-learning group performed significantly better than those in the Traditional Instruction Group, with some students in the e-learning group achieving exceptionally high scores. This aligns with the U.S. Department of Education's (2010) evaluation, which found that students in e-learning courses often perform better than those in traditional face-to-face settings, particularly when the e-learning is collaborative or instructor-directed.

Table 5. Test of Significant Difference of Pre-test and Post-test in Each Group

Group	Tests	Mean Difference	Df	Computed t-value	Effect Size	Description
Traditional Instruction	Post Test	6.630	26	12.17**	3.38	Large
	Pre-test					
E-learning	Post Test	7.926	26	15.66**	4.41	Large
	Pre-test					

** $p < .01$; * $p < .05$

Table 5 shows a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test mean scores for both the Traditional Instruction and e-learning groups, with the post-test scores notably higher in each case. For the Traditional Instruction Group, the mean difference was 6.630 [(t(26) = 12.17; $p < 0.01$), and for the e-Learning group, it was 7.926 [(t(26) = 5.66; $p < 0.01$), indicating substantial improvements in student performance. The effect sizes were large for both groups, with Cohen's d coefficients of 4.41 for the e-learning group and 3.38 for the Traditional Instruction Group, suggesting that both instructional methods significantly impacted student achievement in Science. These findings align with studies indicating that e-learning guiding questions and reflective prompts can enhance student learning outcomes. However, while e-learning offers flexibility and convenience, it may lead to feelings of isolation due to its often solitary nature. Despite this, e-learning has advantages over traditional methods, such as quicker access to supplementary information and reduced time to locate resources. Nevertheless, some studies, like those by Chang et al. (2014) and Al-Qahtani and Higgins (2013), found no significant difference between blended e-learning and traditional methods, highlighting the varied impact of e-learning based on its implementation and the specific educational context.

The study revealed that both the traditional instruction and e-learning groups started with similar performance levels, as indicated by their identical mean pre-test scores of 7.52, reflecting a satisfactory level. However, as the study progressed, the e-learning group outperformed the Traditional Instruction Group in formative and post-tests. The formative test results showed mean scores of 50.41 for the e-learning group and 46.70 for the Traditional Instruction Group, indicating a very satisfactory level of performance for both. However, the e-learning group demonstrated a higher achievement, with more students scoring in the very satisfactory to excellent range. In the post-test, the e-learning group continued to excel with a mean score of 15.44 compared to the Traditional Instruction Group's 14.15, again showing a higher number of students in the e-learning group achieving excellent scores.

The analysis found significant differences between the two groups, with the e-learning group consistently performing better in both formative and post-tests. The effect sizes calculated through Cohen's d indicated that the e-learning platform had a moderate impact on student performance during the formative assessments and a similar moderate effect on their exit performance in the post-test. Furthermore, significant improvements were observed within each group when comparing pre-test and post-test results, with the e-learning group showing a more significant effect size ($d = 4.41$) compared to the Traditional Instruction Group ($d = 3.38$), suggesting that the e-learning platform had a powerful impact on improving student performance in Science. These findings highlight the effectiveness of e-learning platforms in enhancing student achievement compared to traditional instruction learning methods.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn: The e-learning platform had a moderate impact on student performance with the t-test results for the formative tests [(t(52) = 3.26; $p < 0.01$), a mean difference of 3.704 and an effect size ($d = 0.88$). Similarly, there is a significant difference between the mean performance of the groups that is [(t(52) = 2.52; $p < 0.05$], with a mean difference of 1.296 and an effect size ($d = 0.68$), showing that the e-Learning platform also moderately improved exit performance. The null hypothesis stating that there is no significant difference between the mean scores of the traditional instruction group and the e-learning group on the pre-test, post-test, and formative tests is rejected.

Likewise, there is a substantial improvement in student performance where the Traditional Instruction Group has a mean difference of 6.630 [(t(26) = 12.17; $p < 0.01$), and for the e-Learning group with 7.926 [(t(26) = 5.66; $p < 0.01$)] with large effect sizes for both groups of 4.41 for the e-Learning group and 3.38 for the Traditional Instruction Group (following Cohen's d coefficients), showing a significant impact on student achievement in Science. Similarly, the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference between the mean scores on the pre-test and post-test of the traditional instruction group and the e-learning group is also rejected.

The study recommends increasing student awareness of e-learning benefits and ensuring students and educators understand the preferred communication methods of learning, such as face-to-face interactions or digital platforms in e-learning like Google Classroom and social or learning chatbox, in delivering the curriculum. Pedagogical concerns in e-learning should be prioritized, emphasizing active learning and fostering more significant interaction between students and e-learning administrators that may start from school-

based Learning Action Cells, policy, and program or project development as deemed needed by the school. Additionally, incorporating animation and multimedia into course materials is suggested to enhance student learning. Incorporating this into the existing curriculum may start from completing the whole course material for the entire school year and be integrated into class or school computerization, making it available for teachers and students to utilize. Future research should focus on how elementary institutions can best prepare teachers to use and teach with e-learning platforms effectively.

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